

PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS ON THE TEACHING OF LITERATURE IN THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES

Ozoda Odiljon kizi Abdullaeva

Student of Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635544>

Abstract. This article discusses the pedagogical views of our early medieval scholars and thinkers in the teaching of science, especially literature. Their methodological views are analyzed in detail from today's point of view.

Keywords: value, knowledge, theory, methodology, art word, expressive reading, story, psyche

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ НА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ В РАННЕМ СРЕДНЕВЕКОВЬЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются педагогические взгляды наших раннесредневековых ученых и мыслителей на преподавание наук, особенно литературы. Подробно анализируются их методологические взгляды с сегодняшней точки зрения.

Ключевые слова: ценность, знание, теория, методика, художественное слово, выразительное чтение, рассказ, психика, сочетание.

INTRODUCTION

When it comes to the theory or methodology of teaching literature, we can see that the process of studying it has been going on until recently. Among the Turkic peoples, the issues related to the study of literature have been reflected since ancient times, from the monuments of Orkhon Enasoy in the V-VII centuries. In general, the issues of bringing literature to a level that can affect the human psyche, understanding the essence of the artistic word have always been of great socio-spiritual importance in the life of the peoples of the East, especially the Uzbek people. The didactic views of Eastern scholars pay close attention to the issue of teaching methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Human morality, on the other hand, is based on the study of science and enlightenment, and spiritual maturity is based on reason and behavior. According to thinkers, the realization of the ideas of humanity, the attainment of spiritual perfection depends on deep knowledge and enlightenment. That is why they glorify science at the level of universal values, call on all members of society to acquire knowledge, and appreciate the role of science in human spiritual life.

Abu Nasr al-Farabi, a great Central Asian thinker and encyclopedic scholar of the early Middle Ages, was awarded the title of "Aristotle of the East." philosophical ideas are extremely important. According to Pharoah's teaching, man has the ability and power of the mind, which is not present in all other bodies, the power of the mind and speech, which distinguishes him from other bodies in nature and gives him the ability to rule over it. In this worldview, Farobi pays special attention to the mental processes that serve to know things, to enrich the human mind with knowledge, to make it scientific and enlightened. In many of his treatises, such as "On the Achievement of Happiness," "The Classification of the Sciences," "What You Need to Know Before Studying Philosophy," and "The Virtue of Science and the Arts," emphasizes that

development depends on knowledge. Farabi also emphasized in his book, *The Origins of Science*, that it is a great art to read a work of art expressively and to tell a story based on what you have read. Indeed, in today's literature class, when students are told a story, or when they are asked to read or write what they have read independently, they develop a better understanding of the work of art, but also the ability to think independently.

Abu Ali ibn Sina, known in the West as Avicenna, one of the great encyclopedic scholars of Central Asia who made a great contribution to the development of world science, tried to shed light on the issues of ethics and moral education on a philosophical and pedagogical basis. He emphasizes the role of parents in family upbringing, especially: "When a child is born, first of all, the father should give him a good name, and then bring him up well." Ibn Sina, reflecting on the effect of the work of art on the human psyche, states that when the ghazal is heard, the state of the soul is prone to joy and laughter, or to sadness and weeping, especially when mourning and hajj are mentioned. We all know that today's students live in the information age, in an increasingly globalized world. So, when they listen to works of art in literature classes, but also poems that shake people on different topics, of course, different influences do not go unnoticed in their psyche. For example, the 7th grade literature textbook includes the poem "Onaginam" by Mirtemir, a great representative of 20th century Uzbek poetry. As you read this poem to the students, tears well up in your eyes, and you can see how much the students respect their mother and how much they are fulfilling their childhood duty to their mothers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Abu Rayhan Beruni, another great medieval encyclopedic scholar, emphasizes that knowledge is the key to the study of universal values. An enlightened person is a fighter for the destiny of society, for the destiny of human beings, far from all evils. "The benefit of science is not to greedily accumulate gold and silver, but to obtain what man needs through it," he said. In general, Abu Rayhan Beruni, as a great patron and fan of science, believed that the prosperity of the country is in the flourishing of science, and the happiness of man is in his knowledge and enlightenment. In his works, he cites examples from educational poems and proverbs, through which everyone strives for goodness according to the commandments of his heart, not to show mercy and honor for the sake of artificial prestige and fame. emphasizes the need. Abu Rayhan Beruni also analyzes and compares the unique works of world literature, including the Avesto, an ancient monument of the peoples of Central Asia and Iran, as well as various works of Arabic and Indian literature, such as *Kalilla and Dimna*.

The great scholar Yusuf Hos Hajib recommends that education and upbringing be inextricably linked, emphasizing that boys should complete several arts and crafts, which will shape their future lives. , is necessary for the development of society. In general, Yusuf Hos Hajib in his epic "*Kutadg'u bilig*" with his wise advice on the virtues of language, honesty, purity, humility, love and fidelity, mercy, patience, , being caring and kind to others encourages you to do everything in its place and on time. In short, it guides man to perfection in keeping with the demands of the times.

One of the great figures of early medieval culture in Central Asia, Mahmud Qashqari, one of the most famous and influential scholars in the field of linguistics, especially in the study of Turkic languages, has his views on reading separately, together and in large numbers in his *Devonu lug'otit turk* .

CONCLUSION

In short, the methodological views of the above scholars are of great importance today. Today, we think that we can achieve our main goal if we can apply their valuable ideas on the impact of literature and the word of art on human education and spiritual development in the classroom.

References

1. Methods of teaching literature / textbook: K. Husanbaeva, R. Niyazmetova: 2018. - 352 pages.
2. Literature: A textbook for the 7th grade of general secondary schools. Revised 4th edition / K. Yuldashev, B. Kasimov, V. Kadyrov, J. Yol Doshbekov. - T.: «Sharq», 2017. - 368
3. Uzbek folklore. O. Madayev. - T.: MUMTOZ SO`Z, 2010
4. Textbook for the 5th grade of general secondary schools / S. Ahmedov, B. Kasimov, R. Kochkarov, Sh. Rizayev. - T.: "Sharq", 2020
5. Abdullayeva, O. O. (2021). Work on questions and assignments in the study of Abay's work. Academic research in educational sciences, 2 (3), 4-9.
6. Abdullayeva, O. O. (2021). To develop students' sense of patriotism based on the work of Ibrayim Yusupov. Academic research in educational sciences, 2 (3), 176-180.
7. Botirboyev, F. P., Abdullayeva, O. O., & Shermatova, U. S. (2021). Work on questions and assignments in the study of the work of Oljas Suleymanov. Academic research in educational sciences, 2 (4), 2013-2018. <https://doi.org/10.24411/2181-1385-2021-00834>
8. Abdullayeva, O. (2021) The impact of works of art on the human psyche. Scientific progress, 1 (5), (pp. 272-275)
9. Abdullayeva, O. O. Q. (2021). The role of modern technology in teaching the Uzbek language. Scientific progress, 1 (5)
10. Abdullayeva, O. O. Q. (2021). USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN ORGANIZING LITERATURE LESSONS. Studencheskiy Vestnik, 16 (161)
11. Abdullayeva, O. O. Q. (2021). TEACHING HORSES TO BE USED IN THE UNITY AND PURPLE. Scientific progress, 2 (1)
12. Abdullayeva, O. O. Q. (2021). INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH AND THEIR ROLE IN LITERATURE. Scientific progress, 2 (1)
13. Ozoda Odiljon qizi Abdullayeva. (2021) Working with interactive methods in the study of the life of the immortal Umarbekov. Science and education, 2 (5)
14. Ozoda Odiljon qizi Abdullayeva. (2021) Effective ways to teach the life and work of Saida Zunnunova. Science and education, 2 (5)
15. Ozoda Odiljon qizi Abdullayeva. (2021) Interactive methods in the study of Said Ahmad's stories. Science and education, 2 (6)
16. Ozoda Odiljon qizi Abdullayeva. (2021) Methods of teaching fairy tales in general secondary education. Scientific progress, 2 (2)
17. Ozoda Odiljon qizi Abdullayeva. (2021) Interactive methods in teaching Chingiz Aitmatov's White Ship. Scientific progress, 2 (2)